

Application of the Project Based Learning Model in Improving Creativity and Entrepreneurial Skills for Independent Entrepreneur Students at the Kupang Negeri Polytechnic Campus

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ABSTRACT: Implementation of the Independent Curriculum requires that lecturers carry out learning and teach students using a student-centered learning model. Project Based Learning (PjBL) is a studentcentered learning method.

Entrepreneurship is a science that emphasizes attitudes and creativity, where creativity is a skill needed in the digital era.

The Merdeka entrepreneurship program is one of the independent learning programs in the Merdeka learning curriculum at the Merdeka campus as a certified independent entrepreneurship development program to prepare individuals who are competent in developing businesses. Learning is used with a project based learning model. This learning activity includes individual and team learning. The aim of the research is to determine the process of implementing the project based learning model in increasing students' creativity and skills in making business products and the results of increasing students' creativity and skills in making business products through the project based learning model in learning creative product entrepreneurship courses for the even semester of the 2022/2023 academic year.

This research is classroom action research with a project based learning model. The research subjects were students in the 6th semester of the Public Sector Accounting study program, totaling 100 students. Implementation from April to August 2023, consisting of 3 cycles, with stages: "Observation, Planning-Action & Reflection". Actions are carried out by researchers and collaborators who are tasked with observing and recording any existing developments. The data collection method used is observation. Data analysis was carried out by measuring the creativity and skills of the product results of several types of businesses, namely by presenting them in the form of tables and percentages. The research results show that initial observations show that many groups still lack creativity and skill. In implementing the project based learning (PJBL) method, students experience an increase in their creative thinking and skills after being given action. Increased creativity in making student business products in learning creative products and entrepreneurship in semester 6 2022/2023 amounted to 84.66%, and increased skills in making student business products amounted to 81,25%. The description above shows that the project based learning (PJBL) method can increase student creativity and skills in learning creative products and entrepreneurship.

KEY WORD: Creativity, Skills, Creative, Products, Project Based Learning

INTRODUCTION

In general, from Indonesia's point of view, the number of educated unemployed or college graduates in 2017 was recorded at 630,000 people or around 8.85% of the number of unemployed in Indonesia which reached 7 million people. The large number of educated unemployed is a problem of higher education in Indonesia.

Improving the quality of education in higher education is an urgent need for immediate improvement. Quality improvement can basically be done with a strategy of changing one of the subsystems: people, structure, technology and organizational processes (Asmawi, 2010). It is hoped that the Independent Learning - Independent Campus (MBKM) policy can be an answer to these demands. Through MBKM, students have the opportunity for 1 (one) semester or the equivalent of 20 (twenty) credits to study outside the study program at the same university; and a maximum of 2 (two) semesters or the equivalent of 40 (forty) credits studying the same study program at a different university, studying at a different study program at a different university; and/or learning outside higher education (Kemendikbud, 2020). Various forms of learning activities outside of higher education, including doing internships/work practices in industry or other workplaces, carrying out community service projects in villages, teaching in educational units, participating in student exchanges, conducting research, carrying out entrepreneurial activities, making studies/

independent projects, and participating in humanitarian programs. All these activities must be carried out with guidance from the lecturer.

One of the independent learning activities that boosts and develops the spirit of students to become entrepreneurs is entrepreneurial activities.

Entrepreneurship development is seen as a strategic step in an effort to help overcome the nation's economic problems. According to the Minister of Small and Medium Enterprises Cooperatives at the time of the launch of the National Entrepreneurship Movement (GNK) in 2011, the number of entrepreneurs had only reached 0.24% of the total population of Indonesia. Even though the target of the 230 million Indonesian population was 4.6% of entrepreneurs, this was far from which are expected. For this reason, the ministry is encouraging universities to pay more attention to campus alumni who become potential entrepreneurs or young startups. Some time ago the Kupang State Polytechnic campus was trusted to carry out an independent entrepreneurial activity program by developing students using a project based learning model. In implementing entrepreneurship learning involving 1001 student participants from eight universities in the city of Kupang. The independent entrepreneurship program is implemented using a project based learning approach.

Creative and entrepreneurial products are learning that directs and educates students to continually develop and be able to become creative, innovative entrepreneurs following current developments in the food service industry. as the core of learning 1. According to Thomas et al. project based learning (PjBL) is a learning model that provides teachers with the opportunity to manage learning in the classroom by involving project work. According to Trianto, project-based learning is defined as teaching that tries to link technology with everyday life problems that are familiar to students, or school projects³. From the opinions above, it can be concluded that project based learning is a project-based learning activity, where students and teachers carry out a project whose implementation is linked to everyday life problems. According to the Buck Institute for Education⁴, several characteristics of project based learning include: 1) students as decision makers and creating frameworks; 2) there is a problem whose solution is not determined beforehand; 3) students as process designers to achieve results; 4) students are responsible for obtaining and managing the information collected; 5) carry out continuous evaluation; 6) students regularly review what they have done; 6) the final result is a product and its quality is evaluated; and 7) the class has an atmosphere that tolerates mistakes and changes. From the characteristics mentioned above, it is known that the active role of students is very necessary to create a situation where the project that is the task and will be carried out by the student can run well. For this reason, mutual cooperation in completing tasks is very necessary so that the objectives of project based learning can be carried out well

With the hope that if students master entrepreneurship then when students graduate, students are expected to be able to open a business and be able to create employment opportunities so that they don't just depend on job vacancies.

Student creativity

Creativity has various meanings, some say creativity is an attitude, behavior or action, but there are also those who define creativity as just a way of thinking.

Mc. Pherson in Hubeis states that creativity is connecting and reassembling knowledge in the human mind which allows him to think more freely in generating new things, or producing ideas that surprise others in producing useful things.

Piers suggests that the characteristics of creativity are as follows:

Have high drive, Have high involvement, Have great curiosity, Have high perseverance, Tend to be dissatisfied with the establishment, Full of self-confidence, Have high independence, Free in making decisions, Accept yourself, Happy humor, Has high intuition, Tends to be interested in complex things.

Meanwhile, Wallas stated that the creative process includes four stages. In detail, the creative process can be explained as follows: Preparation Stage, namely a person prepares himself to solve problems by learning to think, looking for answers, asking people, and so on. Incubation stage, where the individual seems to temporarily escape from the problem, in the sense that he does not think about the problem consciously, but "incubates" it in the pre-conscious realm. This stage is important in the process of generating inspiration. , Illumination stage, where ideas begin to emerge to solve the problem, Kohler describes this stage with the words: "Now, I see it", Verification stage, where new ideas or creations that emerge must be tested against reality. Here critical thinking is required. In other words, the process of divergence (creative thinking) must be followed by a process of convergence (critical thinking).

Apart from that, the characteristics of creativity according to Guilford's opinion, quoted by Dedi Supriadi (1994: 7), argue that the characteristics that characterize the ability to think creatively include a) Fluency, namely the ability to produce many ideas,

including: having an opinion, being free in think, be confident, and think long term. b) Flexibility, namely the ability to come up with various kinds of solutions or approaches to problems, including: being able to generate an idea, having initiative, being independent or working hard, seeking new experiences. c) Originality, namely the ability to generate ideas in an original way, including: responding to something, having an active imagination. d) Elaboration, namely the ability to express the influence of ideas in detail to make ideas become reality, including: being free to express opinions and detailing things, always finding, researching and realizing ideas, acting towards new experiences.

e) Redefinition, namely the ability to state the influence of ideas in detail to make ideas become reality, including: being free to express opinions and detailing things, always finding, researching and realizing ideas, acting towards new experiences. The lecturer, as a motivator, is very important in starting and maintaining a student's business. This role is so that the lecturer guides decision making and the willingness to learn so that learning goals are achieved.

Student Skills

The definition of skill is the ability to use reason, thoughts, ideas and creativity in working on, changing or making something more meaningful so that it produces value from the results of the work. An example of a skill is something like a skill sewing, cooking skills, singing skills, writing skills, and so on. People who can be said to be skilled people are people who do or complete their work quickly. The term skilled is usually used to describe a person's varying levels of ability. Skills are the ability to operate work easily and carefully (Sri Widiastuti, 2010: 49). Meanwhile, according to Hari Amirullah (2003: 17), the term skilled is defined as an action or task, and as an indicator of a person's level of skill. Skill is a consistent degree of success in achieving a goal effectively. According to Hottinger (Hari Amirullah, 2003: 18), movement skills based on genetic and environmental factors can be divided into two, namely, (a) phylogenetic skills, which are skills that are innate from birth, which can develop as the child gets older. (b) ontogenetic skills, which are skills resulting from practice and experience as a result of environmental influences.

PICTURE 1

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used in this research is the Classroom Action Research method. Classroom action research begins with a problem felt by the lecturer himself in learning. Classroom Action Research is described as a series of steps (a spiral of steps). Referring to the spiral model from Kemmis and Mc Taggart (David Hopkins, 1993: 48), where the research process consists of three cycles.

This research was carried out in three cycles, each cycle with stages: 1. Pre-project. At this stage the lecturer prepares all research tools before conducting the research. 2. Planning In more detail, the planning steps are: a) Finding problems in class, b) Looking for the causes of problems in class during online teaching. c) Choose a problem. d) Designing the instrument. e) Planning learning steps 3. Implementation Implementation of learning is as follows: Cycle 1, namely with Opening, Apperception, conveying learning objectives. 4. Observations Observations are carried out by collaborators and researchers. Where both observe and document things that happen during the action. 5. Reflection Researchers and collaborators discuss the results of action observations regarding deficiencies found in the cycle after completion as a basis for preparing the next action plan. The criteria for success in this research are as follows:

1. The number of students who are declared creative reaches 80%. 2. 80% of students' skill scores get a score in the competent category.

Assessment of student creativity and skills using observation sheets, student creativity by measuring knowledge and results. The assessment using scoring procedures includes (Sudjana, 2002:67): Observation of lecturer activities is carried out using lecturer activity observation sheets which are filled in by observers at each meeting in a cycle and as reflection material. Assessment of student creativity using student activity observation sheets which are filled in by observers at each meeting in each cycle. Student activity observation sheets can be assessed using the formula:

$$\text{Student creativity} : \frac{\text{Total student scores}}{\text{Number of Students}} \times 100\%$$

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH OBJECT

General Description of Research Subjects before action, namely the learning conditions of the previous odd semester and the beginning of the even semester in this class, creativity can be categorized as quite creative and the value of skills cannot be measured validly

RESULT

Cycle I Data

1. Results of Cycle 1 Planning. Observations for Cycles 1 to 3, both offline and practical, were carried out from May 15 to July 23 2023. Those who were treated were semester 6

4. The basic competencies used are basic competencies that researchers consider appropriate to the current learning conditions, namely from the knowledge aspect, namely Analyzing business opportunities for goods/services products and Planning business products for the skills aspect. The steps taken before implementing the first cycle with the project based learning model are preparing materials, lesson plans, creating scenarios, lesson plans, instruments and other supporting tools. 2. Results of Cycle 1 Implementation a. Initial activities: The lecturer opens the lecture by saying hello, inviting prayer, and taking attendance of students offline. Apart from that, the lecturer also conveyed motivation about the importance of worship and general learning motivation. Appreciation of material about culinary business products by giving WAG a power point about various types of business products and previous types of culinary businesses, then the learning objectives are clearly conveyed what they want to achieve at the end of the learning. b. Core Activities The stages in the core activities in the project based learning model consist of 6 steps carried out by both lecturers and students in the learning process, namely: 1) Online meeting 1: a) Stage 1, Determining the Project (basic questions) the lecturer presents the problem that occurs and tries to involve students to participate in determining any project. The questions asked: what types of culinary product businesses can sell, fulfill needs, are easy to promote, are attractive, and what is the system for marketing these culinary products safely. b) Stage 2. Designing project completion (designing project planning) students prepare project work designs by analyzing culinary business products by preparing menus to be sold, number of portions, calculating selling prices, packaging methods, marketing and promotion methods, as well as bookkeeping business reports in detail. simple about the profits and losses of the business. c) Stage 3. Arrange a student schedule, make an agreement on the production process time, promote their product/business using various social media, and determine the location for the production process. 2) 2nd meeting directly:

a) Stage 4. Evaluating the project process and results (monitoring students and project progress), students carry out production practices according to their plans, with shopping activities, material preparation, production, portioning, packaging, calculating selling prices, marketing, reporting sales results. students make interim business reports

b) Stage 5. Prepare reports & presentations (test results)

c) Stage 6. Evaluation of experience. Students make reports and present briefly and respond to other groups and lecturers.

3. Cycle 1 Observation Results Results of observations in the first cycle using the project based learning method for culinary business students

4 provides another form of learning, students are more enthusiastic about learning. This can be seen in the results of observations of student activities which are supported by observations of lecturer activities.

The results of these observations are: a. Lecturer Activities In general, the implementation of learning using the Project based learning method was carried out well, although there still needs to be improvements in the course of learning. b. Student creativity Things that need to be improved are, explanations of the project based learning learning model, and lecturer scenarios in coordinating the course of student discussions, so that nothing will deviate from the rules (order). The results of the implementation of student observations in implementing the project based learning model are that there are still a high number of students who are only creative enough at 79.6%, so there is still a need to increase creativity in general.

c. Student skills

Observations of student skills were taken using observations made by lecturers and collaborators. The results showed that student skills tended to be in the quite competent category at 61.75% of all respondents and there were still some who were less competent.

d. Reflection on Cycle 1. From the observations from the lecturers and collaborators above, it can be concluded that in cycle 1 there were still many students in the quite creative category, 65.60%. Due to this being the first time practicing during this pandemic, there are many obstacles to online guidance in business preparation and limited communication between lecturers and students. Practical readiness too

CONCLUSION

From the research results, it can be concluded that the project based learning model is able to increase creativity by 81.85% and skills by 84.66% in preparing student business products in learning creative products and entrepreneurship in the even semester 2022/2023. The suggestions from the research results include that student learning creativity in the learning process can be fostered apart from the students themselves, and it is no less important than mentoring and guidance from several parties, including from parents, campus (lecturers), and friends. Student creativity and skills can be formed by adopting positive habits, namely giving students the opportunity to be responsible individually or as a group in entrepreneurship.

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